

Literacy as a Strategy for Improving the Quality of Education

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to provide an understanding of the important role literacy plays in the world of education for the progress of students for the nation and state. Literacy exists and is provided from an early age as a means to increase students' knowledge so that education becomes much better. The type of research used is qualitative research with a descriptive approach. The data collection technique used by the author is literature study. Literacy provides many benefits, improving the quality of human resources for educational progress.

INTRODUCTION

In the world of education in particular, writing is an important thing that is needed. Lesson test books and other reading books are learning tools for students in school institutions from elementary to tertiary level. Without writing and reading, the process of scientific transformation would not be possible. Therefore, we must continue to strive to encourage and guide the younger generation, including pupils and students, to cultivate literacy activities. One of them in this case is literacy or reading. Reading is one of the activities in literacy. Literacy cannot be separated from the world of education.

Literacy is the ability to read and write. Literacy development is important to pay attention to, because literacy is an initial ability that every individual must have to live life in the future. Literacy learning will get optimal results if it is taught from an early age so it is called early literacy. (Dalimunthe, 2019). Antoro (2017) states that reading is one of the activities in literacy activities. Through reading, students can absorb knowledge and explore the world which is beneficial for their lives. Reading is an activity in literacy activities which is the key to educational progress. (Muliastri, 2019)

Lerner (1988) reading ability is the basis for mastering various fields of study. If children at early school age do not immediately have the ability to read, then they will experience many difficulties in studying various fields of study in the following grades. The National Institute for Literacy, defines literacy as "an individual's ability to read, write, speak, calculate and solve problems at the skill level required for work, family and society." (Dalimunthe, 2019). The demand for reading skills in the 21st century is the ability to understand information analytically, critically and reflectively.

By increasing students' interest in literacy, they can support educational progress for the nation. Because education in Indonesia continues to be improved from time to time, so that Indonesia's human resources (HR) can keep up with the increasingly rapid developments in science and technology in this era of globalization. Education is a teaching and learning or guiding activity carried out by educators for students with the aim of moral improvement, intellectual training which leads to changes in students' behavior for the better. (Marisyah, 2019)

Education has an important role in creating quality human resources. Education is a systematic process to improve human dignity holistically, which means that every individual can find self-identity, purpose in life and meaning of life through the relationships they have with society and their spiritual values as well as the natural environment around them. Education is important because it is considered a benchmark for seeing the prosperity and progress of a nation. (Azizah, 2019)

Schools as one of the component institutions in the education sector are a very strategic place in order to prepare quality human resources. (Budiharto et al., 2018) One of the important factors for advancing a nation is reliable and quality human resources (HR). Reliable and high-quality human resources are needed by a nation more than abundant natural resources (SDA) which then don't know how to manage them. (Kharizmi, 2015) and is an ongoing

educational development effort to improve the quality of education in a sustainable manner. Education will have a big contribution to shaping a person's character. In this case, the state has a strong role in improving the quality of education. (Azizah, 2019)

Literacy is one way to improve the quality of education for the future of students themselves, the nation and the country. So, based on the above, the author presents the points in this article, related to literacy as a strategy to improve the quality of education, namely the author presents how literacy plays an important role in the world of education?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Literacy comes from Latin, namely *ligeratus*, meaning marked by letters, understanding letters or being educated (Sri Wachjuningsih, 2022). Literacy is known as a person's ability to read and write. However, in a broad sense, literacy can be defined as a person's ability/skill in obtaining and processing information to develop understanding, increase knowledge and potential.

The various types of literature include:

1. Literacy read and write
2. Numeracy literacy
3. Scientific literacy
4. Digital literacy
5. Cultural and civic literacy

Literacy is developed from an early age, so children are able to increase their interest in literacy for their future, as are the benefits of literacy

1. Develop skills in language aspects, especially the ability to read, recognize letter symbols, numbers, vocabulary, writing, how to communicate, speak, express opinions, etc.
2. Develop critical thinking
3. Develop potential

Education is a basic effort to provide spiritual and cultural values that exist in the lives of people who have culture in every generation, not only in the form of "maintenance" but also aims to advance and develop culture (Ab Marisyah, 2019). Education means the process of humanization or better known as humanizing humans, therefore we should be able to respect human rights. Education in a broad sense is an activity or process of teaching and providing education that can occur anywhere and at any time.

Education is a systematic process to improve human dignity holistically, which means that every individual can find self-identity, purpose in life and meaning of life through the relationships they have with society and their spiritual values as well as the natural environment around them. This can be seen from the educational philosophy which is basically useful as a medium for actualizing the three most elementary dimensions of humanity, according to the Ministry of National Education in 2005, including (a) an affective quality that radiates from the quality of faith and devotion, ethics and aesthetics, as well as

noble morals and character. sublime; (b) a cognitive focus on thinking and intellectual capacity in exploring knowledge and developing and mastering technology; and (c) psychomotor which is seen in the ability to develop technical skills and practical skills. These three dimensions will attempt to prepare students to be able to live life (Azizah, 2019).

METHODOLOGY

In this research, the type of research used is qualitative research with a descriptive approach. The data collection technique used by the author is literature study. Literature study is research by reviewing the literature required in research that is carried out diligently. In this case the author collects, records and manages various information from various reading materials, such as journals, books and internet sources related to the type of research.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Literacy is an important issue in the world of education in Indonesia. In its history since independence, Indonesia has struggled to increase literacy. Starting with an illiteracy eradication program and efforts to improve skills. Literacy itself in English Literacy comes from the Latin language *Littera* (letters) whose meaning involves mastery of writing systems and the conventions that accompany them.

Literacy has long been synonymous with reading and writing activities. However, the Prague Declaration in 2003 stated that literacy also includes how a person communicates in society. Literacy also means social practices and relationships related to knowledge, language and culture (UNESCO, 2003). The UNESCO Declaration also states that information literacy is also related to the ability to identify, determine, find, evaluate, create effectively and in an organized manner, use and communicate information to overcome various problems. These abilities need to be possessed by each individual as a condition for participating in the information society, and are part of basic human rights regarding lifelong learning.

Literacy itself is part of the education process. Education plays a role in shaping a person's character, one of which is through literacy which is built in the educational process. Therefore, to increase the literacy index of the Indonesian nation, it is necessary to carry out activities that familiarize Indonesian children with reading and writing. As a national movement, the habit of reading and writing must start from early childhood education to higher education. Therefore, literacy is of course very important to improve in schools. Basic literacy skills in the form of the ability to read and write must be a top priority in the world of education. There are many benefits that can be obtained from reading, namely building interest in reading and being able to meet intellectual demands, increasing interest in a field, and being able to increase concentration.

To increase literacy in the school environment, the School Literacy Movement or GLS was formed, developed by the government based on nine priority agendas (Nawacita) related to the duties and functions of the Ministry

of Education and Culture, especially Nawacita numbers 5, 6, 8, and 9. The Nawacita points referred to are (5) improve the quality of life of Indonesian people and society, (6) increase people's productivity and competitiveness in international markets so that the Indonesian nation can progress and rise together with other Asian nations, (8) carry out a national character revolution, (9) strengthen diversity and strengthen Indonesian social restoration. The four points of Nawacita are closely related to the literacy component as capital for the formation of human resources that are quality, productive and competitive, have character and are nationalistic. In order for schools to be at the forefront of developing a literacy culture, several strategies are needed to create a positive literacy culture in schools

1. Conditioning the physical environment to be literacy friendly, such as students' work being displayed in the school environment in turns, preparing reading books in the corner of the classroom and the principal having dialogue with all students
2. Changing the social and affective environment as a model of literate community and interaction, such as giving awards to students, celebrating holidays with literacy themes to develop students' literacy interests and involving all school staff in developing students' literacy interests
3. Strive for the school to be a literate academic environment, such as forming a school literacy team when needed, providing sufficient time to read well so as not to sacrifice other interests, and preparing sufficient numbers of fiction and non-physical books at school.

The goals of literacy in students' self-development include:

1. Identifying the purpose of the text, target readers, and text implicatures, the ability to create various forms of text, and the ability to choose strategies, as well as appropriate skills for using various media, the ability to apply literacy for various purposes in various scientific, cultural, situational and media contexts
2. Able to formulate ideas creatively, able to solve problems, able to use high level skills, carry out in-depth interpretations and able to intelligently understand texts
3. Instill in students the value and power of literacy, so that students are motivated to be literate throughout life and realize that literacy is able to solve problems, explore and influence the world
4. Develop student independence as students who are creative, innovative, productive and at the same time have character.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMENDATIONS

Literacy cannot be separated in the world of education because literacy can build interest in reading and we are able to meet intellectual demands, increase interest in a field, and are able to increase concentration for students and for the formation of quality, productive and competitive human resources, with character, as well as nationalists, in improving the quality of education for the nation and state. School is an effective place to support students' literacy development, so the school must always develop strategies to continue to increase interest in literacy.

FURTHER AND RESEARCH

This research still has limitations so further research needs to be done on this topic "Literacy as a Strategy for Improving the Quality of Education".

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